

were allowed to feed on each plant for 2 and 4 d, and then were transferred to healthy 7- to 10-d-old TN1 seedlings at 1 insect/seedling, where they remained until they died.

An average 13% of the insects transmitted the disease agent. Incubation period was 15-33 d. About 10% of the infective insects could transmit the disease agent until they died. Disease agent retention was 18-43 d. Incubation period in plants was 10-28 d. In addition to orange leaf symptoms, young leaves of inoculated seedlings

Electron micrograph of MLO in a sieve tube of rice leaves infected with orange leaf (20,000X).

were ragged and twisted. Infected seedlings died 3-4 wk after symptoms appeared.

Under the electron microscope, ultrathin sections of leaf tissue from plants infected with each isolate showed MLO in the sieve tubes. The MLO were bounded by a unit membrane and a pleomorphic 50-1100 nm in diameter (see figure), which indicates that the pathogen causing orange leaf in the Philippines is not a virus and is most likely a MLO. *S*

Tungro (RTV) incidence in Andhra Pradesh in 1984

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RTV is a major problem in India. Since 1970, it has been recorded in Oct-Nov in

isolated areas of Andhra Pradesh. In 1984 rabi and kharif it reached epidemic proportions (Table 1). Except for IR50, most varieties grown in Andhra Pradesh are susceptible.

Disease surveys were conducted in Ranga Reddy, Medak, Karim Nagar, West Godavari, Guntur, Prakasam, Nellore, and Chittoor Districts from Jan

to Nov 1984. Field diagnosis used visual symptoms and the IRRRI iodine test. Transmission tests were conducted on all samples with positive iodine tests. Selected virus isolates from TN1 were evaluated in serodiagnostic tests using antisera from IRRRI. The tests confirmed that the disease was RTV (Table 2). *S*

Table 1. RTV-affected areas in Andhra Pradesh in 1984.

District	Months	Varieties affected	Area affected (ha)	Severity
Ranga Reddy	Jan-Feb	Tellahamsa	8,000	Severe
Medak	Mar	Tellahamsa	1,500	do-
Karim Nagar	Mar	Tellahamsa	1,500	Moderate-severe
West Godavari	Jan-Feb	BPT1235	5,000	do-
Nellore	May-Jun	IET2508	3,000	do-
Chittoor	Jun-Jul	Rasi	5,000	Severe
		IET2508		
Prakasam	Oct-Nov	NLR9674	15,000	do-
		MTU9029		
Guntur	Oct-Nov	NLR9674	15,000	do-

Table 2. RTV incidence^a in rice varieties grown in RTV epidemic areas during 1984.

District	Variety	Planting date	RTV incidence (visual)	Iodine test	Transmission	GLH population
Medak	Tellahamsa	Oct 1983	H	+	+	M
	RNR1446	Nov 1983	H	+	+	M
	IR50	Nov 1983	L	-	-	-
Ranga Reddy	Tellahamsa	Nov-Dec 1983	H	+	+	M
Nellore	IET2508	Mar 1984	H	+	+	M
	Rasi	Mar 1984	H	+	+	H
	IR50	Mar 1984	L	-	-	L
	NLR9672	Aug 1984	H	+	+	M
Prakasam	NLR9674	Aug 1984	H	+	+	M
Chittoor	Rasi	May-Jun 1984	M	+	+	M
	IET2508	May-Jun 1984	M	+	+	M
	IR50	May-Jun 1984	-	-	-	-
	RGL 2624	Jun 1984	M	+	+	M

^a L = low, M = moderate, H = high.

Granular fungicides for controlling blast (BI)

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BI caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* is increasing in Tamil Nadu. Foliar fungicides are advocated for disease control. Sometimes, however, lack of sprayers prevents proper spray application. Granular fungicides require no special equipment. Soil-applied granular fungicides are absorbed by roots and systemic action protects rice stems, nodes, panicles, and foliage. Granular fungicides require fewer applications and less labor to apply than do sprays.

We evaluated probenazol (Oryzemat 8G), pyroquilon (Coratop 5G), chlorbenthiazole (S. 1901 6G), and IBP (Kitazin 17G) for BI control. Highly BI-susceptible IR50 was planted in Oct-Jan 1984-85 in a randomized block design with four replications.

Fungicides were applied at tillering and panicle initiation at 30 and 40 kg formulated product/ha. IBP, which has a much higher active ingredient content